

D2.1 Report on the Collaboration platform for DIHs

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www.dihnet.eu

About the DIHNET.EU project

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is carried out by TNO, TecNALIA, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BluMorpho and FEDIL, have strong experience in DIHs and well connected to the EU DIH community.

Executive Summary

This document has been created to show the main features of the DIHNET platform that was launched for the consortium members only on the 21/01/2019. This deliverable (D2.1) gathers all relevant features related to the online platform which contains all the information and services that can help DIHs stakeholders to be more aligned among themselves and better support their final users.

This document shows the work developed providing the proper on-line platform architecture to support the DIHNET community, and explains how each of the new features will contribute to reach the goals of the initiative.

This deliverable includes screen shots of the website and other features in order to show the functionalities of each of the tools that will be used to create a sustainable European network of DIHs.

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1 Introduction

DIHNET.EU's main objective is to enhance the collaboration between the different stakeholders from the European DIH Community with a wide range of services, information and tools that will help DIHs and agents to communicate, align, collaborate and synchronize activities.

For this purpose, the project has established a platform architecture to support the DIHNET.EU, focused namely on the website and the community, to facilitate information exchange, access to important data and benchmarking of initiatives.

These tools fulfil different purposes:

- **Website:** will be the entry point of the interested audiences to get a first overview of the DIHNET project.
- **Community:** will act as a repository of information, where the materials used by the different DIH networks are made available. Also, it facilitates information exchange, access to important data and benchmarking of initiatives. Also, it will be a place for discussion and feedback.

2 Website

The DIHNET website <https://dihnet.eu/> offers key information about project objectives, outcomes and the rationale of the pan-European Network of DIHs. This website became live the 21/01//2019. The website is the institutional communication tools, describes the project activities, tasks, offers information about project partners and main events.

The DIHNET.EU community will be the main entry point to all information related to the DIH ecosystem, including news, articles, announcements, questions funding opportunities, events, etc.). The website will be an important tool to support the alignment of the communication of the DIH agents to their individual target audiences and to create a common European image. Also, it will be the place for DIHs and network of DIHs, to meet each other, connect and interact.

Figure 1: DIHNET.EU Website

Among the information included in the DIHNET.EU website is the following:

- Explanation about the vision and mission of the DIHNET.EU project

- Access to training and resources on **How to develop a DIH**, through the contents generated by the I4MS project, mainly a **Mentoring Programme** focused on six key non-technological issues on how to further develop Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) namely:
 - Ecosystem assessment
 - Business models for DIHs
 - Building a Business Plan
 - Brokerage for innovation
 - Use cases
 - Access to finance

Figure 2: DIHNET.EU Website: How to develop a DIH section

- Information about the **Catalogue of DIHs** created by the Joint Research Centre, and the role of DIHNET.EU project.
- A **Digital Maturity self-assessment Tool (DMS)** is currently being developed and will be hosted at the DIHNET website. This tool will allow to quick scan the digital maturity of the DIHs.

Figure 3: DIHNET.EU Website: Digital Maturity Scan tool section

- A **News section** which contains all the latest news and relevant information of the DIHNET.EU project and of interest for DIHs.

3 Community

3.1 Objective of the community

Become the central information point and discussion of DIHs and networks of DIHs. Be the place where interested stakeholders visit to get information, share their opinion and learn from others.

The DIHNET.EU community includes communication and services to foster working in common, facilitate collaboration and find relevant information in order to support the creation of a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

Link available here: <https://dihnet-community-1.fundingbox.com/>

Figure 4: DIHNET.EU Community microsite

3.2 Target audiences of the DIHNET.EU online community and project offer

- **Sectoral and technology oriented DIHs that aim at providing services to SMEs:**
 - Reinforcement of services deployment: Provide them with information how to improve their services with regard to a systematic addressing the needs of their customers through the organisation of learning between the DIHs;
 - To facilitate pan-European connections between individual DIHs with a platform, both to create learning mechanisms as well as initiate collaboration
- **Regional DIH initiatives, including regional DIH networks as well as regional initiatives like Vanguard:**
 - To reinforce alignment and synchronisation of the deployment of services and increase the impact of regional and national expenditures on digitization, developing a smart specialisation strategy on DIH.
 - Facilitate access to pan-European capacities (infrastructure and expertise) by offering tools to find these capacities they can easily implement at regional level;

- **EU DIH networks** (H2020 Innovation actions and CSAs, EC Preparatory Actions, Interreg projects), as well as **EU supported digital transformation initiatives**: EFFRA, IAs and CSAs in I4MS, SAE, photonics, robotics, HPC CPS/IoT. Projects like Smart Factories and Connected Factories also are included:
 - Aligning the activities of the different initiatives and creating a coordinated communication approach to the EU DIH community (improving impact);
 - Creating a learning mechanism between the initiatives to enhance efficiency and increase impact;
 - Create common resources to be used, like general communication materials, lists of contacts;
 - Organize a common approach to the DIH Catalogue, so information can be shared between the initiatives. The objective is also to create a governance structure.
- **European Commission services in charge of DIHs development and policy**:
 - Aligning the activities and policies devoted to support DIHs and Regions;
 - Obtain direct feedback from the policy target (DIHs, EU initiatives part of the pan-European network, DIHs networks).
 - Bring the ecosystem directly involved in the implementation of the Digital Europe Programme together, being able to select best practices, offer inspirational practical cases to lagging behind regions.

3.3 Impact and KPIs

The indicators that will be used to evaluate the performance of the activities related to the DIHNET.EU online community are the following:

KPI	KPI name	target
KPI 2.1	# of on-line platforms ready for supporting collaboration	1 platform
KPI 2.2.	# of thematic communities that are active and on-going by the end of the project	At least 8
KPI 2.3.	# of connections among community members suggested through the matchmaking tool.	At least 80% of community members with completed profile will receive suggestions
KPI 2.4.	# of common calls/challenges or surveys launched with the open calls builder, by the CSA but also by the community	12 (4 per year)
KPI 2.5.	# of training activities in community building and platform use	3 webinars
KPI 2.6	# of digital maturity scan tools	1 tool

In order to maximise the impact of the community and create a sustainable ecosystem that is active, and capable to share information, benefit from it and takes profit from all the available resources, FundingBox will organise different webinars in order to facilitate the use of the platform.

The webinar will be very practical, DIHs will be invited to share content to practise, connect with other members, post articles, events and other type of information. Tips to increase the interest of the

published information will be provided and the tool to create communities will be also explained. Also, in case there are some open calls or surveys open, the project will take profit of this webinars to incentivise participation. During the training the different features will be presented through examples to ensure its comprehension and see the potential of each of the tools for DIHs.

The webinars will be also an interesting event to attract new users and raise interest among the DIHs about the different tools that will be put at their disposal during the project.

3.4 Community structure

- **Central Information Point:** Static content that gathers the information in an easy and retrievable way.
 - **Articles:** news, pieces of information related to the content created by project partners, interviews and conclusions related to the project work. They should include a call to action or questions for the audience to enable the discussion.
 - **Announcements:** important information that doesn't require any action by the members of the community: for instance, open calls or funding opportunities.
 - **Questions:** this section gather all the questions posed in the community by any member.
 - **Events:** announce events of interest for DIHs.
 - **Showcase:** best practices to illustrate how DIHs are doing in the different areas covered by the project.

- **Spaces:** with real-time chats aligned with the working groups of the DIH network, but also with the contents and different activities that will be developed to offer support to DIHs. Each one of the spaces needs to be fed with attractive content in form of articles and announcements. Specific activities to foster 1:1 interaction will be organised, such as:
 - Introduce yourself: Tell us who you are, what brought you here and what would you like to talk about in the DIHNET.EU Community
 - News & Events: Stay tuned about the latest news and events
 - Criteria of the DIHs Catalogue: Share with us your vision on what should be the criteria of the EC to include DIHs in the catalogue of DIHs created by the JRC? Do you agree with the current ones? Make your suggestion!
 - Q&A: Do you have questions? Do you have answers? Feel free to ask to the community members any doubt or concern you have, we will all together try to answer them!

Figure 5: DIHNET.EU Community: real-time chats

- **Forms Gallery and Open Calls Management System:** Templates, benchmarking templates and questionnaires to assess the performance of DIHs and identify their needs. The tool will offer also templates for the DIHs to drive their growth and create a sustainable and attractive offer to the end-users.
- **Tool for Setting Up Local Communities:** In order to encourage DIHs to create local communities following the same type of approach, so at the end we will have a community of communities.
- **Matchmaking Tool:** The matchmaking system allows all participants to identify profiles that could be of their interest and connect with them to find synergies and collaboration opportunities. This matchmaking will work in a way where each user will receive according to their interest's potential profiles of people with similar interests making easy for them to connect and hold one to one conversations.

The matchmaking service is born with the aim of connecting the members of this ecosystem. The DIHNET online community, powered by FBA, provides the core technological infrastructure and the proper on-line environment for attracting the target audiences of the project and contributing to reach the goal of connecting the DIHs and the different networks where every stakeholder can create and promote its own profiles. The matchmaking features of the platform will be embedded within different sections of the platform; besides an overall matchmaking space that will allow peer-to-peer engagement between users.

The Matchmaking service is being built upon the community platform developed from FundingBox. This is a powerful communication and analytics tool for building and organizing communications at scale, and learning how people interact. On top of it, several features have been developed to empower the dynamism of the community and among them, the matchmaking capabilities play a crucial role to make a more engaging community to retain users, create synergies and foster business and research relationships.

At the matchmaking system all participants can identify profiles that could be of their interest and connect with them to find synergies and business. This matchmaking will work in a way where each user will receive according to their interest's potential profiles of people with similar interests making easy for them to connect and hold one to one conversations. Every stakeholder can create and promote its own profiles. The matchmaking features of the platform will be embedded within different sections; besides an overall matchmaking space that will allow peer-to-peer engagement between users.

Any user in the matchmaking section will be able to see three main sections:

- **Community members**, where all the users of the community will be showcased with their profile picture and description
- **Community staff and ambassadors**, where we are highlighting those profiles of the users that are more active in the community and of influencers and partners for the Project
- **Matchmaking**, where profiles will be suggested according to the user preferences. The user will be able to send invitation requests to the users suggested and once accepted they will be able to live chat in a private one to one chat.

Figure 6: DIHNET.EU Community directory: matchmaking tool

3.5 Content

Each partner is responsible of dynamizing the online space, under his/her ownership alongside the Working group, offering information in form of articles, reports, and inviting them to actively participate. It is important to take advantage of the different project activities, such as surveys, polls, interviews, policy recommendations etc, to create helpful content, as well as of the figure of Ambassadors or experts that can contribute offering relevant content for the ecosystem.

3.5.1 Partners: profile and main task

As the main objective is to develop a collaboration within the EU DIH community, the project will be centred around different topics that have been identified as key topics to foster DIHs collaboration:

Table 1: partners contributions to the project

Partners/activities	EXPERTISE OFFERED	CONNECTIONS	TOOLS
TNO	Specialisation strategy: customer demand, regional strengths, gap analysis, portfolio of services	Connection with policy-makers	Guidelines and materials to facilitate commitment, webinars, best practices, lessons learnt 30 Interviews. Templates. Benchmarking schemes.
TECNALIA	Methodology to update/upgrade JRC catalogue	Connect with EU DIH community	Good examples Digital maturity scan tool. Templates. Capacity building/testing facilities?
FBA	Funding Community building	DIHs community	Platform infrastructure. Matchmaking, best practices, & training
ER	Communication materials for policy makers	DIHs networks	Comm& dissemination activities
BM	Business models	Attract private investment to the network of DIHs	Best practices, collaboration scheme with funding organisations at EU level. 2days' workshop. MoU. Sustainability model
FEDIL	Community	Link up with start-ups, SMEs & midcaps (DIHs customers)	Events

3.5.2 Content provision proposal

Using inbound marketing techniques to attract members through **relevant and helpful content**, adding value at every stage in the attraction and conversion to an active user journey. With inbound marketing, potential members for the DIHNET.EU online community will **discover DIHNET.EU platform** through channels like presenting the project in events, disseminate among the DIHs networks, search engines and **social media**, among many others.

The **use of Ambassadors**, or experts that contribute to the community offering content in form of articles, webinars or other might be also considered as part of the strategy in order to offer a variety of information and contributions, and as a way to attract new audiences and facilitate organic growth.

The table number 3 summarises how based on the different project activities and partners expertise different types of content can be shared in the online community.

FundingBox will provide guidance to project partners giving ideas and suggesting ways to make content available in different formats:

Table 2: project activities and types of content to be provided

ACTIVITY – TOOLS*	CONVERSION INTO COMMUNITY CONTENT
Webinars/ trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Q&A ○ Articles
Best practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Showcase ○ Interview/Article ○ Call to action: look for further examples, ask this DIH your questions,... ○ Foster 1:1 interaction by introducing the person behind this best practice
Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article ○ Article+ Q&A ○ Discussion around topic of interest: every Friday from 11:00-11:30
Interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article about this DIH ○ Conclusions of all interviews
Polls/survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article with the results ○ Live poll: meet the experts and let them know what you think about....
Benchmarking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Get feedback from users and ask to share experiences
Matchmaking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Invite DIHs to introduce themselves and their offer
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article about the event ○ Foster the matchmaking opportunities before the event.
MoU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Article about the activity explaining the level of engagement and what will mean to have this MoU.
Topics of expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Articles ○ Q&A ○ Reports: propose discussions ○ Open questions to the members. ○ Templates ○ Feedback on the methodologies proposed

3.6 Community set-up: next steps

The steps to be followed in order to set-up the DIHNET.EU online community infrastructure and first content describing the different features and spaces is detailed in the table below:

Table 2: steps to be followed to create the DIHNET.EU online community

DATE OF IMPLEMENTATION	ACTIVITY	PARTNER RESPONSIBLE
February 2019	Decide on the title for the spaces to be created and first contents we want to share	ALL
March 2019	Communication strategy running to support community growth	ER
March 2019	At least 50 stakeholders contacted to invite them to the community and provide content/discussion.	ER+ALL
March 2019	First contents for the community ready	ALL
22 March 2019	European robotics forum- official launch	
March 2019	Set up platform infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The community will be created but only few users will be invited to test the features and respond the questionnaire. ○ Private community 	FBA
March 2019	Questionnaire to be sent to DIHs to select the WG	TECNALIA
April 2019	Description and objectives of each of the WG- ACTION PLAN. This activity will contribute to create new spaces or select topics for discussion	TECNALIA + Each partner
September 2019	1 st results assessment	FBA, TNO+ALL
April 2019 -Sept 2021	Outreach activities contribute to bring members to the online community	ER

4 Conclusions

DIHNET aims to be the largest online community of DIHs and Networks of DIHs in Europe with the aim of allowing the DIHs stakeholders to share the information provided by the project and to facilitate interaction among the members. It provides features for organising and managing private or public real-time communications. The ecosystem will be invited to use this community to build their networks, to channel their communications and to share their information.

It is important to mention that the added value of this community is that sharing the different information DIHs and Networks of DIHs will learn from each other, bring together information and foster the discussion among all key players.

To make it grow several actions and campaigns will be carried out to attract members, spreading the right message to the right target audience. However, the goal is also to retain the new members, and that will be done by offering them exclusive content only available on DIHNET.EU online community in order to get an active, vibrant and thrilling community. Project partners will closely work together to coordinate the actions and make sure they get the best performance.

As a final objective, the online community also aims to bring DIHs and networks of DIHs together in order to foster the collaboration among all of them, provide them with tools that contribute to facilitate this interaction and benefit from the learning, experiences and success stories of this big community.